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“CONCEPTUAL PROPOSITION ON BINARY-BASED GENDER COMPOSITION FRAMEWORK”

The conceptual or theoretical proposition on Binary-Based Gender Composition Framework (BGCF) arises to explore alternative conceptual or theoretical framework of the current understanding that we have on the composition of human gender and how it is being expressed.

This conceptual or theoretical proposition seeks to simplify whether we are born male or female (sex), our feelings if we are a man, woman, both, or neither (gender identity), the way we dress or behave towards another (gender expression), and who do we love and like or have a crush on (sexual orientation).

In this conceptual or theoretical proposition on the framework of gender composition, I'm suggesting that all individuals have that male-ness and female-ness in them regardless of their actual core gender. This male-ness or female-ness of an individual is what I call “Gender Essences”. These gender essences of an individual can be quantified into percentages for simplicity.

I mean, I know that it's hard to prove a gender based in numbers, or in this case - percentages without proper philosophical research and reflection (theory) or empirical and scientific research (real-life experiences) but it's a mental relief for me just to get the concept or the idea of a binary-based gender composition framework out in the public.

So, before continuing with this conceptual or theoretical proposition, the readers must understand that this concept or theory is still in its infancy stage and still needs some deep philosophical and empirical research.

Below are the two core genders of this concept or theory, the male gender and the female gender and the three expressions associated with it.

THE CORE GENDERS

In this conceptual or theoretical proposition, the core genders are male genders and female genders and are defined as individuals born naturally as either a biological male or a biological female with male essences or female essences of 100% or lower. The core genders are always present in an individual and is the base of the gender composition no matter if that individual identifies itself as a man, woman, both, or neither.

1. Male Gender

100% (-) Male Essence

As one of the core genders in this concept or theory, this figure represents the male-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological male. Male essence here is at 100% or lower. Individuals of this figure are attracted to their opposite gender, the female gender with 100% essences or below.

2. Female Gender

100% (-) Female Essence

As the other core gender in this concept or theory, this figure represents the female-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological female. Female essence here, like its opposite gender, the male gender, is also at 100% or lower and is also attracted to the male gender with 100% essences or below.

GENDER EXPRESSIONS

1. Bi-Genders

Bi-Genders are those individuals born naturally as a biological male or a biological female with both having 50% higher or lower male essences or female essences.

Male and Female Bi-Gender

50% (±) Male Essence	50% (±) Female Essence
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This figure represents the male-ness and female-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological male or a biological female. It has 50% higher or lower male essences and 50% higher or lower female essences respectively. Individuals in this figure are attracted to both male gender and female gender with 100% essences or below and with other bi-genders. The slang used for individuals being a bi-gender is a term called “double-blade”.

2. Cross Dressers

Cross dressers are individuals born naturally as a biological male or a biological female. Two types of cross dressers are identified as gay cross dresser and lesbian cross dresser.

Gay Cross Dresser (GCD)

15% (±) Male Essence	85% (±) Female Essence
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This figure represents the female-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological male. It has a 15% higher or lower male essences but higher in female essences with 85% as its minimum or maximum. Individuals in this figure are attracted to male genders with 100% male essences or below and with male bi-genders.

Lesbian Cross Dresser (LCD)

85% (±) Male Essence	15% (±) Female Essence
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This figure represents the male-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological female. It has an 85% higher or lower male essences compared to just 15% minimum or maximum of female essences. Individuals in this figure are attracted to female genders with 100% female essences or below and with female bi-genders.

3. Typical Expressers

Typical expressers or the non-cross dressers are individuals born naturally as a biological male or a biological female. Gender essences of typical expressers differ significantly from the cross dressers, the gay cross dresser and lesbian cross dresser. Two types are identified here, the gay typical expressers (GTE) and the lesbian typical expressers (LTE).

Gay Typical Expresser (GTE)

25% (±) Male Essence	75% (±) Female Essence
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This figure represents the female-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological male. The male essences here is at 25% higher or lower while the female essences are at 75% higher or lower. Gay typical expressers (GTE) are attracted to male genders with 100% male essences or below and with male bi-genders.

Lesbian Typical Expresser (LTE)

75% (±) Male Essence	25% (±) Female Essence
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This figure represents the male-ness of an individual born naturally as a biological female with a 75% higher or lower male essences and 25% higher or lower female essences. Individuals here are attracted to female genders with 100% female essences or below and with female bi-genders.

With the conceptual or theoretical proposition on the framework for gender composition expressed above, I hope that every reader on this Binary-Based Gender Composition Framework (BGCF) to be open on the idea or concept that there are alternative ways – simpler ways, though not definitive, on how to address the basic nature of human gender composition and how it is being expressed individually.

Other genders not mentioned here, take note that the baseline gender composition are the core genders, the male gender and the female gender. If you need to quantify your gender and how you express it, use the core genders as your baseline.